

DEVELOPMENT AND USE OF NONVERBAL COMMUNICATION IN CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDERS (ASD) AND THEIR PARENTS

Glogova V.

Assistant Prof., New Bulgarian University, 1618 Sofia, Bulgaria 21 Montevideo Str.
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Abstract

The purpose of this publication is based on a literature review to highlight the main aspects of nonverbal communication and its application to create a stronger lasting "parent-child" relationship and in the education of children with ASD. The main approaches to teaching children with ASD are reviewed- learning through games, video movies, through their peers with typical behavior, through art. In all these, albeit diverse, approaches to learning, several common and important features stand out: 1. Reciprocity in activities - the child with ASD must feel the care and special attention and attitude towards him; 2. Encouragement to creativity, stimulation and integration of personal skills; 3. Absence of stress factors and the therapist's desire to build an environment and relationships with an atmosphere of calm and safety. 4. Nonverbal communication is the basis of each of the learning approaches. 5. The listed approaches can be applied in an integrated manner.

Keywords: autism, disorders, nonverbal communication, children, parents, therapy

INTRODUCTION

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a diagnosis that includes significant social communication deficits/delays along with restricted patterns of interests and behaviors (17). There are no accurate statistics on the number of children with autism in Bulgaria. According to unofficial data from practice (7), there are about 140,000 children with autism in the country, while globally, according to the World Health Organization (2016) (54), ASD is found in one out of 160 newborn children in the world.

Communicating and reading the communication signals of the child with ASD is the first step in any successful therapy. People with ASD often also have language difficulties and according to a study by Brignell et al. (2018) (13) about 25% to 30% of children with ASD fail to develop functional language or are minimally verbal. The ability to communicate effectively is a fundamental life skill, and communication difficulties can have a number of adverse outcomes, including lower academic achievement, behavioral difficulties and reduced quality of life.

A number of authors (4) highlight nonverbal communication as a powerful tool in conducting therapies for people with ASD, which complements, and in many cases it is even more appropriate than verbal communication. Nonverbal communication is the basis of the so-called Augmentative and alternative communication (AAC), which is used mostly for children with ASD who are low verbal (25) ,(13).

According to specialists such as Siegel (1973) (47), Scharoun et al. (2014) (45) and others. physical activity, sports and dance (coordinated movement), as an important part of therapeutic activities related to nonverbal communication, have proven their benefits regarding the possibilities of improving communication skills and social development of children with autism. The application of dance movement therapy (DMT) as a syncretic method can "optimize the psychomotor behavior of youth with ASD (50).

An important aspect of the therapeutic activities is strengthening the proactivity on the part of parents of

children with ASD and improving communication between them through movement. The options for practicing the so-called "joint dyadic movement parent-child (with ASD)" and their results have been studied in different directions - from arguments for choosing the most optimal activities and programs (29), to the influence of this type of activity on the stress level and quality of life of parents of children with ASD (1).

The purpose of this publication is to highlight the main aspects of nonverbal communication and its application to create a stronger lasting "parent-child" relationship and in the education of children with ASD.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

National and word databases of scientific publications such as NALIS Union Catalog, Elsevier, Scopus, Research gate were systematically searched using keywords related to "ASD", "children", "non verbal communication" etc. The more important results of the review related to the purpose of the study are systematized in several sub-points, at the end of each specific conclusions are summarized.

RESULTS

1. Symptoms of ASD - classification and development

Based on a series of studies by Lord et al. (1994) (34), Gotham et al. al (2007) (20), Wiggins et al. (2015) (53) the following indicative classification of symptoms in ASD can be made:

1 Group: Communication and social symptoms. Includes:

- Language difficulties – most people on the autism spectrum have difficulty communicating with other people. This often becomes apparent in early childhood. All delays in speech development and nonverbal communication should be evaluated by a qualified professional.

- Eye contact and nonverbal communication – Poor eye contact and avoidance of eye contact are common symptoms among people with autism. Other nonverbal communication difficulties may include recognizing and using facial expressions, physical gestures and general body language.

- Tone of voice – Some people with autism may have difficulty regulating or modulating the tone of their voice. As a result, they may speak too loudly, too softly and/or in a monotone voice.

2. Group: Behavioral symptoms

- Repetitive behaviors – many people with autism may perform the same behavior repeatedly. This may include rocking, spinning or clapping their palms and arms, or flicking their fingers in front of their eyes. They may also play with toys or other objects in unusual ways, such as tirelessly spinning coins or plates and repeatedly pressing light switches.

- Ritual Behavior – This may include eating the same foods at every meal or watching the same videos over and over. They can even become quite upset soon after any slight change in plans.

- Self-injury – Some people on the autism spectrum hit their head on the ground or wall, bite their hands, or excessively rub or scratch their skin. There are many ways to treat these behaviors, including medical, sensory, nutritional, and behavioral approaches.

Bertilsson et al. (2022) (8) derive the following characteristic symptoms in ASD related to the general structure of movement quality: 1) reduced postural control; 2) deviant muscle tone and tension; 3) deviant sensory processing; 4) lack of conscious awareness; 5) difficulties with the limits of body movement; 6) coordination of movements (including breathing); 7) lack of preliminary preparation of movements; and 8) need for cognitive thoughts to control movements. According to the authors, the bodies and minds of people with ASD must constantly protect themselves from sensory impressions "from within" or from the environment, causing emotional stress and obscuring the meaning of their movements. Their body's reactions become restrained, choppy and hesitant.

Study Anderson et. al (2011) (5) examined trajectories of change in symptoms of irritability, hyperactivity, and social withdrawal, as well as predictors of such behaviors in youth aged 9–18 years with ASD and a control group with non-spectrum developmental delays. Children with more severe core features of autism had consistently higher irritability and hyperactivity scores over time than those with broader autism spectrum disorder and non-spectrum delays. Across all diagnoses, hyperactivity behaviors showed the greatest improvement. According to the authors, social withdrawal worsened with age for a significant proportion of youth with ASD, but not for those in the control group. Compared to youth without autism spectrum disorder, children with ASD showed greater heterogeneity in maladaptive behavior trajectories.

Gotham et al. (2015) (21) demonstrate that people with ASD are at particular risk for problems related to affect and anxiety. Although female symptom levels increase at a faster rate during adolescence, males with ASD appear to have elevated levels of depressive symptoms at school age that are maintained into young adulthood. Anxiety was most positively related to "verbal intelligence" and when low, both anxiety and depressive symptoms were greater in ASD than non-autistic study participants.

Conclusions:

1. With age, the ASD-symptoms change or are not as pronounced. 2. Knowing is not enough, understanding (interpreting) the symptoms (including movement patterns and emotional responses) of people with ASD is necessary, which can facilitate constructive interaction and communication, which has important implications for the design of therapeutic interventions .

2. Social difficulties in autism spectrum disorders

Autism spectrum disorders (ASD) are characterized by social and communication difficulties in everyday life, including problems in recognizing emotions. At the same time, affected individuals have a wide range of intellectual abilities and language skills. The majority of people with ASD have mild to moderate intellectual disability, but others demonstrate average to above average intelligence. Some of them have specific abilities in areas such as music, mathematics or memory that greatly exceed their general level of functioning (so-called autistic savants are known). Some people with ASD do not speak at all, while others express themselves verbally quite freely. The abilities of people with autism spectrum disorder vary widely. Some of them need help in their daily lives, while others can live and work with little or no support. (2)

ASD is characterized by impairments in social interaction (eg, social awareness, verbal and nonverbal communication) and repetitive, restricted behaviors, interests, or activities (eg, atypical movement, play and engagement with objects or subjects, atypical sensory behavior). Communication and interaction difficulties may include delayed language development or lack of spoken language and impairments in nonverbal communication such as limited eye contact, reduced facial expression and limited expressive gestures. In addition, people with autism often have difficulty processing non-literal and pragmatic elements of speech. Repetitive, stereotyped behaviors may include eye pressing, hand gliding, slight staring, and rocking (6). Repetitive, stereotyped behaviors may include eye pressing, hand sliding, slight staring, and rocking.

According to Weiss & Harris (2011) (52) the treatment of social skill deficits remains one of the most challenging areas in meeting the needs of people with autism. Difficulties in understanding social stimuli, in initiating and responding to social offers, and in assessing the effect inherent in social interactions can be confusing for people with autism. Uljarevic & Hamilton (2013) (51) consider that determining the integrity of emotion recognition in autism spectrum disorders is important for theoretical understanding of autism and for teaching social skills. The authors argue that the recognition of happiness is mostly successful in autism, and the recognition of fear is marginally more difficult than the recognition of happiness.

The ability to accurately perceive and interpret emotions from facial expression is fundamental to effective social communication according to Tanaka et al. (2012) (49), who found that patients with ASD generally have impairments in their ability to generalize facial emotions across identities and show a tendency to recognize facial features (eyes, lips) as isolated parts that cannot to connect in an overall expression.

Rogers (2003) (43) explored the potential that gesture analysis may have to help better understand the difficulties of children with specific language impairments and children with ASD. The study compared typically developing children, children with autism spectrum disorders, and children with specific language impairments regarding the use of gestures. Significant group differences were observed in the type and frequency of gesture use.

Conclusions:

Social difficulties in people with ASD generally come from the following reasons: 1. The behavior of people with ASD is in many cases, for most people with typical behavior, qualified as inappropriate, and they tend to put up barriers in communication and social closeness with people with ASD; 2. People with ASD have a problem with the perception of other people's emotions, which affects the empathic bond and hence the social one; 3. For a large part of people with ASD, abstract concepts (including those with a motivational charge) are incomprehensible and foreign - concepts such as "goal", "value", etc. 4. The issue of anxiety, which is to a greater extent in people with ASD and the relationship with socialization, is interesting. At this stage, it has not been proven that anxiety in ASD is due to fear of socialization, but on the contrary, their anxiety can affect their socialization.

3. Diagnosis of ASD and initiation of therapy

According to Daniels & Mandell (2014) (16), the diagnosis of autism is often delayed, resulting in a missed opportunity to provide therapy during a critical period of development. The authors found that the mean age at diagnosis for all autism spectrum disorders ranged from 38 to 120 months and decreased over time. Factors associated with earlier diagnosis included greater symptom severity, high socioeconomic status, and greater parental concern about initial symptoms. Family interactions with the health and education systems prior to diagnosis also influence age at diagnosis. Geographic variation in age at diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder also showed significant differences, suggesting that resources and government policies play a role in early identification of ASD. Early detection efforts should include increased education of parents and caregivers for early recognition of developmental problems, interventions aimed at streamlining the process from first concern to eventual diagnosis, and strategies targeting underserved populations.

May et al. al. (2021) (36) noted that children with a late diagnosis of ASD showed increasing trajectories of emotional and behavioral problems, whereas children with persistent or absent diagnoses showed decreasing trajectories. Between 86% and 74% of children studied by the authors had a reported diagnosis of ASD after 6 years. The findings show that children with ASD need services and supports that can adapt to their changing needs, which may be increasing, decreasing or simply different and sometimes difficult to fit into typical social care.

Hosozawa et al. (2020) (24) found that children with ASD are at increased risk for depression and self-injurious behavior, but whether timing of ASD diagnosis is associated with these outcomes in adolescence is

not yet well-studied. The authors found a linear relationship between the time of ASD diagnosis and depression and self-injurious behavior in adolescence. Later diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder, particularly diagnosis in adolescence, is associated with increased risk of depressive symptoms and self-injurious behavior in adolescence among children with ASD. According to the authors, interventions aimed at earlier diagnosis of ASD and approaches to improve person-environment fit may help prevent secondary mental health problems among people with ASD, especially among those without cognitive delays and as well the late diagnosed.

Conclusions:

Early diagnosis in ASD facilitates and increases the success of therapies. Awareness among people about the characteristics (symptoms, specific behavior) of ASD is important for its detection at an early age by family members or relatives.

4. Nonverbal communication in ASD

According to Iskrov et al. (2018) (26) the incidence of ASD has steadily increased over the past 30 years. The growing number of patients brings to the fore a number of medico-social issues and causes health, social and educational authorities to seek sustainable solutions to this problem. According to Kyriacou et al (2023) (31), autistic individuals have persistent differences in verbal and nonverbal communication, social interaction, restricted and repetitive patterns of behavior and interests, and abnormal responses to sensory stimuli from hyperreactivity to hyporeactivity. Leekam et al. (2007) (32) concluded that more than 90% of children and adults with autism have a sensory response that interferes with their daily lives, and their symptoms are consistent across age groups and IQ levels.

Sigman et al. (1999) (48) found that children with autism, regardless of their level of functioning, were less socially engaged with their classmates than other children with developmental disabilities (eg, those with Down syndrome and children with developmental delays) because they rarely initiated and accepted suggestions for play, not because they were rejected by their peers. Early nonverbal communication and play skills are predictors of peer engagement in children with autism. Based on the results of their study, the authors conclude that improvements in early communication and play skills can have long-term consequences for the later language and social competence of children with autism.

The results of an experimental study by Koegel et al. (2001) (30), showed that children with autism and their typically developing peers played with a comparable number of stimulus (eg, toys), but children with autism engaged in these activities for a shorter time. According to the authors' observations, both children with autism and their typically developing peers engage in similar levels of social interaction with adults. However, children with autism rarely or never engage in social interactions with their peers, whereas typically developing children often engage in social interactions with their peers.

According to Prevezer et al. (2009) (38) one of the main difficulties for children with autism is the development of communication and language, and the earlier this problem is addressed, the more effectively these skills can be improved. Children with autism face enormous difficulties when trying to interact with their typically (typically) developing peers. More children are educated in an integrated environment; however, play skills usually need to be explicitly taught, and the play environment must be carefully prepared to support effective social interactions.

The results of a study by Safira et al. (2020) (44) show that although children with ASD cannot interact clearly through verbal communication, they can express their wishes through nonverbal communication. Children can communicate nonverbally through facial expressions, eye contact, body movement, posture and touch. The meaning of nonverbal communication expressed by each child with ASD has a different interpretation, i.e. it is not possible at this stage to derive unified signs and codes.

A study by Alokla (2018) (3) aimed to determine how special education teachers implement evidence-based practices for nonverbal communication skills of children with ASD. The author interviewed six early childhood special education teachers from preschools in Southern California. According to the interviews with the teachers, the joint attention deficit in children with ASD was overcome with the help of visual aids, toys and basic gestures. Peer learning, functional communication training, and drawing have been found to improve nonverbal communication skills. In addition, children with ASD regularly play with their typically developing peers. The author concludes that the co-educational model can benefit children with ASD and also reduce the negative prejudice that typically developing children may have from their peers in special education classes.

A comparative study by Brignell et al. (2018) (13) on language development showed that children with ASD and those with language impairment produced similar mean language scores that were, on average, lower than typically developing children. The authors found that language progressed at a similar rate for all groups of children, with progress influenced by IQ and language ability rather than social communication skills or ASD diagnosis. Therefore, the verbal communication capabilities of the majority of children with ASD should not be underestimated.

Conclusions:

Communication (including nonverbal) between the therapist and the child with ASD is a two-way process that must be approached from the point of view of the child's current capabilities. Children with autism may have difficulty developing language skills and understanding what others say to them. They also often experience difficulties in nonverbal communication expressed most often in uncoordinated hand gestures, avoidance of eye contact and specific autonomous facial expressions. It is necessary for the therapy to pass through an attempt to interpret the specific behavioral manifestations, empathy, trust, to an attempt to enrich the nonverbal stock of the child with ASD with new

more conventional gestures and words, part of the social vocabulary, using mirror movements, mutual (complementary) games, dance, etc.

5. Stress in parents of children with ASD

After conducting review studies by Miodrag, Hodapp (2010) (35), Bonis (2016) (9), Bradley et al. (2023) (10) and others are adamant that increased stress among parents of youth with ASD is a fact and well documented. The daily life of these parents is completely subordinated to the care of their children. They must protect their child from running away (physically and mentally), handle crises, talk to their teachers about special education needs, avoid sights or sounds that overwhelm their children's senses, take them to therapists or doctors. Added to all this is sleep deprivation, as many autistic children have sleep problems and this reflects directly on their parents. Chronic stressors can deplete the body, especially the cardiovascular, immune, and gastrointestinal systems. Highly stressed parents also experience more mental health problems, including depression and anxiety. Many parents are so focused on their children's needs that they stop thinking about their own health. The reciprocal point is that parental stress affects children with ASD. The authors also report the so-called external factors to increase parental stress. Among them are the accusations of uninformed and malicious outsiders that the cause of the child's disorder is poor care in the family, the social isolation of families with ASD. The stress caused by financial difficulties should not be ignored. Parents of children with autism earn less — and work fewer hours — than people whose children have other health problems or no medical problems at all. Families may struggle to pay for therapies not covered by health insurance or provided by schools.

According to Osborne et al. (2008) (37) many parents have taken on, without training, the role of ASD 'therapists' at home as well. Research has found that highly stressed parents have more trouble following through on their children's behavior plans and implementing autism interventions, which isn't good for either side. Increased parental stress can lead to mental and physical fatigue, withdrawal, powerlessness, exhaustion and unwillingness to truly commit. Result, parent finding a pretext (eg new job for more money, etc.) for less time spent engaging with children in shared activities which generally results in reduced enjoyment by parents and children during shared interactions. Parents with elevated stress reported engaging in shared activities and experiencing synchronicity with their child less often than parents below the clinical threshold.

Conclusions:

Conducting therapies by specialists in various forms to parents of children with ASD in order to improve the possibilities, usefulness and enjoyment of shared activities between parents and children with ASD will reduce the stress of these parents.

6. Specificity of communication between children with ASD and their parents

Shattuck et al. (2009) (46) consider that there is too much of a gap between the age at which children with ASD can be identified and when they are actually

identified (according to the authors this occurs when children are 5-7 years of age), suggesting a critical a need for further research, innovation and improvement in this area of clinical practice, including parent education and awareness raising. Brignell et al. (2017) (12) in turn emphasize the importance of the time when parents begin to feel the first signs of loss of communication with the child with ASD. The authors compared the loss of communication in 7-year-old children later diagnosed with autism spectrum disorder, those with language impairment, and children with typical language development. Communication tools completed by parents were used. As a group, children with autism spectrum disorder showed slower average skill acquisition, with an increasing difference between trajectories, compared to children with typical development and language impairment. Part of all groups have lost skills in at least one area (from children with ASD - 41%, children with language impairment - 30%, those with typical development - 26%). Compared to the other two groups, the most children from the group with ASD have lost skills in more than one domain (autism spectrum disorder (47%), language impairment (15%), typical development (16%). Loss was most common for all groups in the domain of 'emotion and eye gaze "but at a higher rate in children with ASD. A greater proportion of children with ASD also lost skills in gestures, sounds, and comprehension compared to children with typical development but not language impairment. According to the authors, these findings add to the understanding of early communication development and emphasize that the loss is not unique to ASD.

Conclusions:

In order to more successfully support the socialization processes of children with ASD, it is necessary:

1. To lower the threshold of the time of their diagnosis;
2. Detection and reaction at the first signs of loss of communication between the child and the parents.
3. Loss of communication is not unique to ASD.

7. Basic approaches to teaching children with ASD

7.1. Learning through games

Play is critical to young children's development and is an important part of their daily lives, however, according to Jung & Sainato (2012) (27), children with autism often exhibit deficits in play skills and engage in stereotyped behaviors. The authors review studies to identify effective instructional strategies for teaching play skills to young children with autism. As a result, they implemented combined interventions involving alternating individual and group play, as a result of which, according to the authors, children with autism improved their play skills, increased positive social interactions and reduced inappropriate side effects. Six main types of play have been identified, which are applied in different sequences or in combination:

- *exploratory play*- in this game, children's interest is directed towards making the objects or phenomena, instead of playing with them (e.g. touching water, stuffed toy, hot and cold cup, etc.)

- *cause-and-effect play* - children play with toys that need an action to get a result - for example, pressing a button to play music or a drive. This type of play

teaches children that their actions have an effect and gives them a sense of control in the game.

- *toy play* - toy play is teaching children how to play and use toys in the way they are designed - for example pushing a toy car, holding a toy phone to the ear or throwing a ball.

- *constructive game* - in it, children build or arrange things. It involves working towards a goal or product - for example, completing a puzzle, building a tower of cubes, or painting a picture.

- *physical play*- it is related to physical insults and activities of a competitive sports nature. This type of play helps the child develop gross motor skills and supports their body. These types of games provide a chance for the child to explore the environment and interact with other people.

Yanardag et al. (2013) (55) recommended water play as preferred by children with autism and as a means of expanding the knowledge, skills and motor development of these children.

7.2. Learning through videomovies

Riby, Hancock (2009) (41) conducted a comparative study in which they assumed that autism and Williams syndrome (WS) are neurodevelopmental disorders associated with different social phenotypes. While individuals with autism show a lack of interest in socially relevant cues, individuals with SU often show increased interest in socially relevant information. The authors used eye-tracking to investigate how people with WS and autism prefer to watch social scenes and excerpts from movies containing human actors and cartoon characters. The proportion of gaze time spent fixating on faces, bodies, and the screen background was investigated. The results showed that while individuals with autism preferred to pay attention to the characters' faces for less time than usual, people with WS paid attention to the same images for longer than usual. For individuals with autism, the atypical gaze behavior extended to human actors and cartoon images or movies, whereas for those with WS, the atypicalities were limited to human actors.

Kagohara (2010) (28) reviewed intervention studies on the use of video-based instruction to teach adaptive behavior to children with ASD. The conclusions of her study are that, in general, this method has a positive impact on children and helps to some extent to improve their skills.

A study by Carter et al. (2014) (14) compared the responsiveness of children with autism to computer-generated or animated characters and their responsiveness to humans. Twelve 4- to 8-year-old children with autism interacted with a human therapist; a human-controlled interactive avatar in a theme park; a human actor speaking as the avatar; and cartoon characters seeking social answers. The authors found a high level of therapist gestural and verbal responses; intermediate levels of response to avatar and actor; and weakest responses to cartoon characters, even though attention was equivalent across conditions. According to the authors, these results suggest that even avatars that provide lively, responsive interactions are not superior to human therapists in eliciting verbal and nonverbal communication from children with autism in this age group.

The results of a study by Cross et al. (2022) (15) shows the benefits of watching cartoons by children with autism. The authors found that while people with autism may demonstrate poorer recognition of facial emotions when the stimuli are human, these differences are reduced when the stimuli are anthropomorphic. That is, the emotions and actions of the drawn characters are more easily recognized by children with autism. At this stage, for a better deterrence of cartoons, it is recommended that there be less negative stimulation in them (intense scenes with sharp and loud noises, bright, flashing colors and rapidly changing images), that the characters speak in calm voices, the messages to be positive focused on community, friendship and family.

7.3. Teaching children with ASD through their peers with typical behavior

The above-described approaches (7.1 and 7.2.) of teaching children with ASD are mainly applied by their teachers or parents/family members. Studies by Harper et al. (2008) (22) and Alshurman & Alsreaa (2015) (4) found that after implementing a nonverbal communication training program for children with autism by their peer mediators instead of a classical teacher, the same two months after its termination they retained the skills they had been on trained, including shared attention, visual communication, imitation, listening and understanding, indicating what they need, understanding facial expressions and tone of voice. According to the authors, the results of the studies provide a positive direction for "peer training" in nonverbal communication of children with ASD and creation of an effective and continuous communication approach between them and the teacher. Imitation skills, easier identification of favorite visual stimulus, serve as additional motivation for the child with ASD.

7.4. Learning through art

Different types of art offer a wide variety of nonverbal communication and expressive tools for children with ASD. According to Emery (2004) (18), art therapy allows children with ASD to engage in a nonverbal form of self-expression that can convey their experiences in a non-threatening way, as it does not require the use of words, which is often difficult for children with an autistic disorder. Epp (2008) (19) considers that art-based interventions activate the senses of sight, hearing, touch and smell. In addition, art therapists use different materials with different colors and textures. They can be used as a means of sensory regulation for the child. Activities can be tailored to individual clients in a way that gives them a sense of security.

Quintin (2019) (39) reviews research findings showing that music is a significant factor in assessing perception, reward, emotion and related physiological responses and neural circuits in individuals with ASD. People with ASD are greatly affected by music, including pitch perception, musical memory, and identification of music-evoked emotions. Listening to music activates neural circuits of reward and emotional response. The author argues that adults with ASD also activate these systems when listening to music, although there may be developmental differences in the physiological and neural response to music in child-

hood and adolescence, along with the typical behavioral response. The outcome of this review study supports the use of music therapy and education for people with ASD, specifically to improve social skills and communication. Taken together, the reviewed findings provide evidence for music as a strength-based approach in ASD cases to assess reward and emotional response and as a powerful intervention tool.

A study by Rahimi-Pordanjani (2021) (40) shows that the so-called drama therapy (therapy through theater) effectively affects the social skills of children with high functioning autism. Using extensive practice examples with a range of client groups, Haythorne, Seymour (2017) (23) challenge the notion that people with autism are unable to function within the metaphorical realms of imagination and creativity. Their study demonstrates that people with ASD are capable of engaging effectively in creative inquiry and by encountering these processes in the clinical context of drama therapy, life-enhancing changes can be made.

According to Roberts (2018) (42), psychotherapists who use the parent-child model when working with children with ASD describe an improvement in communication and in the relationship between children and parents with the help of art therapy (music, drawing, dance, role-playing). They also observed an improvement in the children's ability to engage in symbolic play, in the way the children felt they were understood, and in terms of their parents' support.

A study by Liu et al. (2021) (33) showed that the combination of an applied behavior analytic intervention with parent-child drawing and creative crafting therapy could more effectively improve the core symptoms and social interaction of preschool children with mild to moderate ASD, reduce mothers' parenting stress and improve their level of hope.

Very popular among art therapies for children with ASD is "sand therapy" (also called "sand play therapy"). According to Bradway (2006) (11), it is a combination of play and art therapy, where the therapist uses a box filled with sand, and the client is provided with miniature toys to create their own imaginary world in the sand itself. Toys can be the most diverse - from domestic animals and dinosaurs to trees, flowers, houses and cars - artifacts of real life. The customer is free to choose which toys to use, then he himself arranges them in the tray/box. The therapist plays the role of observer and rarely interrupts the client, letting him recreate a world that reveals his inner struggles or conflicts. After the sand play is over, the therapist and client often discuss what they observed—the particular choice of toys, the way they were arranged, and the hidden meaning or symbolism within them. The basic idea is that if the therapist provides the client with a safe space, they will use the sandbox to find solutions to their problems on their own. According to studies, sand therapy reduces symptoms of various types of mental illnesses or disorders and increases resilience.

Conclusions:

In all these, albeit diverse, approaches to learning, several common and important features stand out: 1. Reciprocity in activities - the child with ASD must feel the care and special attention and attitude towards him;

2. Encouragement to creativity, stimulation and integration of personal skills; 3. Absence of stress factors and the therapist's desire to build an environment and relationships with an atmosphere of calm and safety. 4. Nonverbal communication is the basis of each of the learning approaches. 5. The listed approaches can be applied in an integrated manner.

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